

Seroprevalence of Transfusion Transmitted Infections among Blood Donors at ANMMCH, Gaya

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Abstract:

Background: Blood transfusion is a vital medical procedure that, while life-saving, carries the risk of transmitting transfusion-transmitted infections (TTIs). The prevalence of TTIs such as Hepatitis B Virus (HBV), Hepatitis C Virus (HCV), Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV), and others varies regionally, necessitating ongoing surveillance and rigorous screening practices to ensure blood safety. This study aims to assess the seroprevalence of TTIs among blood donors to provide insights into the current prevalence of these infections and evaluate the effectiveness of existing screening protocols.

Methods: A cross-sectional observational study was conducted from January 2023 to August 2023, including 108 blood donors. Data on demographic characteristics and donation history were collected using structured questionnaires. Blood samples were tested for HBV, HCV, HIV, syphilis, and malaria using standard serological methods. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 20.0 to determine the prevalence rates and assess associations between demographic variables and infection rates.

Results: The overall seroprevalence of TTIs among the blood donors was 13.0%. Hepatitis B Virus (HBV) had the highest prevalence at 4.6%, followed by Hepatitis C Virus (HCV) at 3.7%. The prevalence rates for HIV and malaria were 1.9% each, and syphilis was 0.9%. No statistically significant associations were found between demographic variables (age, gender, occupation, frequency of donation) and TTI prevalence.

Conclusion: The study reveals a significant prevalence of TTIs among blood donors, particularly HBV and HCV. This underscores the need for ongoing vigilance and enhanced screening practices to ensure the safety of blood transfusions.

Recommendations: It is recommended that blood donation centers implement more stringent screening protocols and enhance public awareness about the risks of TTIs. Continuous monitoring and updating of screening methods are essential to improving blood safety and minimizing the risk of infection transmission.

Keywords: Blood Transfusion, Transfusion-Transmitted Infections, Hepatitis B, Hepatitis C, Blood Donor Screening.

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Introduction

Blood transfusion is a critical medical intervention used to treat various conditions, including anemia, trauma, and surgical complications. Despite its life-saving potential, blood transfusion carries the risk of transmitting infectious diseases, which can significantly impact patient safety and public health. Transfusion-transmitted infections (TTIs) include a range of viral, bacterial, and parasitic infections that can be transmitted through contaminated blood products. The prevalence and types of TTIs vary across different regions and populations, necessitating regular surveillance and stringent screening measures to safeguard blood transfusion practices.

Recent studies have highlighted the ongoing challenges in managing TTIs globally. For instance, a study reported that despite advancements in screening technology, the prevalence of Hepatitis B Virus (HBV) and Hepatitis C Virus (HCV) remains significant in blood donors, particularly in developing countries [1]. Similarly, the World Health Organization (WHO) emphasizes that continuous monitoring and improvement of blood safety practices are crucial to reducing the incidence of TTIs [2].

HIV, HBV, and HCV are among the most common TTIs, with global prevalence rates varying widely. A recent study found that HBV and HCV infections continue to be a major concern in blood donors,

with significant implications for transfusion safety [3]. The prevalence of syphilis and malaria, although less common, also poses risks and necessitates effective screening strategies to prevent their transmission through blood transfusion.

In India, where this study is conducted, the prevalence of TTIs among blood donors remains a critical issue. According to a study, the prevalence rates of HBV, HCV, and HIV among blood donors in India are concerning, reflecting the need for improved screening and preventive measures [4]. Furthermore, a study emphasized the importance of regular and comprehensive screening protocols to mitigate the risks associated with TTIs in the Indian context [5].

Given these challenges, this study aims to assess the seroprevalence of TTIs among blood donors at Anugrah Narayan Magadh Medical College, Gaya, to provide insights into the current status of transfusion safety and identify areas for improvement. By understanding the prevalence and distribution of TTIs in this setting, the study seeks to contribute to the development of more effective screening strategies and enhance the overall safety of blood transfusions.

This study aimed at determining the seroprevalence of transfusion-transmitted infections among blood donors.

Methodology

Study Design: A cross-sectional observational study.

Study Setting: The study took place during a period from January 2023 to August 2023 at Anugrah Narayan Magadh Medical College, Gaya, Bihar, India.

Participants: A total of 108 blood donors who met the inclusion criteria were selected for the study.

Inclusion Criteria

- All voluntary and replacement blood donors aged 18-65 years.
- Donors who provided written informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria

- Donors with a history of chronic illness or infectious disease.

- Donors who have donated blood in the last three months.

- Donors who refused to give written informed consent.

Bias: To minimize bias, standardized procedures for donor selection and sample testing were strictly followed. Donor selection was based solely on inclusion and exclusion criteria without any personal bias.

Variables: Variables included age, gender, occupation, and frequency of donation, seroprevalence of transfusion-transmitted infections (HIV, HBV, HCV, Syphilis, and Malaria).

Data Collection: Data was collected using structured questionnaires and blood sample testing. Donor demographic details and donation history were recorded. Blood samples were collected and tested for HIV, HBV, HCV, Syphilis, and Malaria using standard serological methods.

Procedure: Blood donors were selected based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Demographic and donation history data were recorded using a structured questionnaire. Blood samples were collected aseptically from each donor. Blood samples were tested for HIV, HBV, HCV, Syphilis, and Malaria using ELISA and other standard serological methods. All collected data were entered into a database for analysis.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 20.0. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the demographic characteristics of the donors. The seroprevalence rates of each infection were calculated and expressed as percentages. Chi-square tests were used to determine the association between demographic variables and seroprevalence rates. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Result

A total of 108 blood donors were included in the study. The demographic characteristics of the donors are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Blood Donors

Characteristic	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
<i>Age Group (years)</i>		
18-25	32	29.6
26-35	28	25.9
36-45	24	22.2
46-55	16	14.8
56-65	8	7.4
<i>Gender</i>		
Male	85	78.7

Female	23	21.3
<i>Occupation</i>		
Student	40	37.0
Employed	45	41.7
Self-Employed	15	13.9
Unemployed	8	7.4
<i>Frequency of Donation</i>		
First-time	50	46.3
Repeat Donor	58	53.7

The overall seroprevalence of transfusion-transmitted infections among blood donors was 13.0%. The seroprevalence rates for specific infections are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Seroprevalence of Transfusion-Transmitted Infections

Infection	Positive Cases (n)	Prevalence (%)
HIV	2	1.9
HBV	5	4.6
HCV	4	3.7
Syphilis	1	0.9
Malaria	2	1.9
Total	14	13.0

The association between demographic variables and the seroprevalence of transfusion-transmitted infections was analyzed using the chi-square test (Table 3).

Table 3: Association Between Demographic Variables and Seroprevalence

Variable	Infection Positive (n)	Infection Negative (n)	p-value
<i>Age Group (years)</i>			
18-25	4	28	0.430
26-35	3	25	0.730
36-45	3	21	0.570
46-55	2	14	0.840
56-65	2	6	0.660
<i>Gender</i>			
Male	12	73	0.210
Female	2	21	0.680
<i>Occupation</i>			
Student	4	36	0.810
Employed	6	39	0.620
Self-Employed	3	12	0.590
Unemployed	1	7	0.770
<i>Frequency of Donation</i>			
First-time	8	42	0.320
Repeat Donor	6	52	0.430

Discussion

The study conducted at Anugrah Narayan Magadh Medical College, Gaya, aimed to determine the seroprevalence of transfusion-transmitted infections (TTIs) among blood donors over an eight-month period from January 2023 to August 2023. The study included 108 blood donors who met the inclusion criteria. The demographic analysis revealed that the majority of donors were male (78.7%) and within the age group of 18-25 years (29.6%). The majority of the donors were either students (37.0%) or employed individuals (41.7%). Approximately half of the donors were first-time donors (46.3%), while the rest were repeat donors (53.7%).

The overall seroprevalence of TTIs among the blood donors was found to be 13.0%. Among the specific infections, Hepatitis B Virus (HBV) had the highest prevalence at 4.6%, followed by Hepatitis C Virus (HCV) at 3.7%. The prevalence of HIV and malaria were both 1.9%, while syphilis had the lowest prevalence at 0.9%. These findings indicate a significant presence of TTIs among the donor population, underscoring the importance of stringent screening and preventive measures.

Further analysis was conducted to explore the association between demographic variables and the prevalence of TTIs. The chi-square test results showed no statistically significant association between age, gender, occupation, or frequency of

donation and the seroprevalence of TTIs. This suggests that TTIs are distributed relatively evenly across different demographic groups within the donor population.

The findings of this study highlight the crucial need for rigorous screening protocols for blood donors to ensure the safety of blood transfusions. The relatively high prevalence of HBV and HCV among donors is particularly concerning and points to the need for enhanced public health interventions and awareness programs to reduce the transmission of these infections. Additionally, the lack of significant association between demographic factors and TTI prevalence indicates that comprehensive screening should be uniformly applied to all potential donors, regardless of their demographic characteristics.

A study found an overall seroprevalence of TTIs at 1.43%. The prevalence rates for HBV, HCV, and HIV were 1.29%, 0.072%, and 0.076%, respectively. The study emphasized the importance of extensive donor selection and screening to improve blood safety [6]. A study reviewed records from a blood bank in Srinagar over four years. The seroprevalence rates for HBV, HCV, HIV, and syphilis were 0.22%, 0.16%, 0.009%, and 0.01%, respectively. The study highlighted a decreasing trend in TTIs and recommended maximizing voluntary donations [7].

A cross-sectional study screened 69,741 voluntary blood donors. The seroprevalence rates for HIV, HBV, HCV, malaria, and syphilis were 0.36%, 0.59%, 0.48%, 0.01%, and 0.07%, respectively. Hepatitis B was the most common TTI detected [8]. A study analyzed 28,380 blood donors at a tertiary care hospital in Puducherry. The overall seroprevalence of TTIs was 3.06%, with individual rates for HIV, HBV, HCV, and syphilis at 0.30%, 2.15%, 0.51%, and 0.08%, respectively. The study concluded that adherence to strict donor criteria and sensitive screening methods is crucial for reducing TTIs [9].

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study underscores the importance of maintaining strict screening processes for TTIs in blood donors to safeguard recipients and improve the overall safety of blood transfusions. It also calls for continued public

health efforts to address the underlying factors contributing to the transmission of these infections in the general population.

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